

Syntheses, spectral characterizations, redox properties and DFT computations of $[\text{MH}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{N-heterocycle Schiff bases})]^+$ ($\text{M} = \text{Ru}$ and Os) and their applications to the synthesis of Ag nanoparticles

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Manuscript received online 14 May 2012, revised 31 May 2012, accepted 04 June 2012

Abstract : $[\text{MH}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{L})]\text{PF}_6$ (L^1 : *N*-[(2-pyridyl)methyliden]-2-aminopyridine; L^2 : *N*-[(2-pyridyl)methyliden]-2-aminopyrimidine; $\text{M} = \text{Ru}$ ($\text{L}^1 = 1$; $\text{L}^2 = 2$) and Os ($\text{L}^1 = 3$; $\text{L}^2 = 4$)) are characterized by microanalytical and spectroscopic (FT-IR, UV-Vis, mass spectral and ^1H NMR) results. The ligands are emissive where as the complexes are non-emissive. Electrochemistry of all the compounds show $\text{M}^{\text{III}}/\text{M}^{\text{II}}$ couple; additionally $\text{Os}^{\text{IV}}/\text{Os}^{\text{III}}$ couple is seen in 3 and 4 along with ligand reductions. The DFT computation is carried out to the optimized structures. The spectral and redox properties of the ligands and the complexes are explained on the basis of calculated results. The complexes act as mild reducing agent and has been used to synthesise of silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) from AgNO_3 which are characterized by UV-Vis spectra and HR TEM analyses.

Keywords : Ru and Os-hydrido-carbonyls, diimine chromophore, emission spectra, redox property, DFT computation, Ag-NPs.

Introduction

Chemistry of ruthenium and osmium with polypyridine ligands¹⁻⁵ is an active area of research because of their catalytic, corrosion inhibition, redox, π -acidic diimine, photophysical, photochemical and biological applications. The $-\text{N}=\text{C}-\text{C}=\text{N}-$, function present in polypyridine ligand system has specific interest in the development of coordination chemistry⁶⁻¹⁶. Particularly, the importance of iminopyridine ($\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{N}-2-\text{CH}=\text{N}-$) has been attracted in the last few years¹⁷⁻¹⁹. Furthermore, mixed ligand complexes of ruthenium or osmium with diimine group ($-\text{N}=\text{C}-\text{C}=\text{N}-$), H^- , PPh_3 and CO have been found to be potential catalysts for water-gas shift reaction, CO_2 reduction, and hydroformylation reaction of alkenes²⁰⁻²⁴. Besides, carbonyl complexes of ruthenium such as tricarbonyldichloro ruthenium(II) dimer and tricarbonylchloro(glycinato)ruthenium(II) are very recently used as CO releasing molecules (CORM) which liberate CO to elicit direct biological activities such as, anti-inflammatory and anti-apoptotic properties, promotes cardio protection^{25,26}. All these reasons have aroused interest to characterise new series of ruthenium-carbonyl-polypyridine

complexes. In this article, we present the characterization of $\text{MH}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)_2$ complexes of *N* [(2-pyridyl)methyliden]-2-aminopyridine (L^1), *N*-[(2-pyridyl)methyliden]-2-aminopyrimidine (L^2) (Scheme 1) by spectroscopic studies (FT-IR, UV-Vis, mass, ^1H NMR) and the redox properties are described by cyclic voltammetry. The DFT-TDDFT calculation of optimized geometry has been used to explain the spectral and redox properties of the complexes. Hydrido-metal complexes are selective reducing agents and have been used for the synthesis of Ag-nanoparticles. The AgNPs are characterized by UV-Vis spectra and HR TEM analyses.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and formulation :

The reaction between $[\text{MH}(\text{Cl})(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)_3]$ ($\text{M} = \text{Ru}$ or Os) with *N*-[(2-pyridyl)methyliden]-2-aminopyridine (L^1) or *N*-[(2-pyridyl)methyliden]-2-aminopyrimidine (L^2) under refluxing condition in dry MeCN at dinitrogen environment results in red/red-violet solution. The evaporation to half of its original volume followed by the addition of aqueous NH_4PF_6 giving rise to red product. This

Scheme 1. The ligands and the complexes.

has been purified by crystallisation via diffusion of dichloromethane solution to hexane. The formulations of complex, [RuH(CO)(PPh₃)₂(L)]PF₆ (L¹ = 1; L² = 2) and [OsH(CO)(PPh₃)₂(L)]PF₆ (L¹ = 3; L² = 4) have been supported by microanalytical results (Experimental section). The complexes are diamagnetic and show 1 : 1 conductivity in acetonitrile solution ($\Lambda_M = 130\text{--}150 \Omega^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$).

Spectra and bonding :

The ligands (L) show sharp stretch at 1600–1620 cm⁻¹ and 1580–1595 cm⁻¹ due to the presence of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N}, \text{exo})$ and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N}, \text{endo})$, respectively (Table 1). The complexes [MH(CO)(PPh₃)₂(L)]PF₆ (M = Ru (1, 2) and Os (3, 4)) show a sharp stretch at 1940–1960 cm⁻¹ which corresponds to $\nu(\text{CO})^4$. The $\nu(\text{Ru-H})$ is observed as weak stretch at ca. 2062–2073 cm⁻¹ and $\nu(\text{Os-H})$ at 2090–2095 cm⁻¹. The mass spectral measurement shows the main peak at 838.1 (100%), 839.3 (100%), 928.3 (100%) and 929.4 (100%) for the compounds 1, 2, 3 and 4 res-

pectively (Supplementary materials : Fig. S1 and Table S1).

The electronic spectra of the ligands and the complexes were recorded in acetonitrile. High intense transition in free ligands at 270–276 and 295–297 nm are assigned to ligand-centred charge transfer transitions. An intense broad band centred at 497 nm (1), 486 (2), 531 (3) and 533 nm (4) (Table 1, Fig. 1), absent in free ligand, is assigned to $d\pi(\text{M}) \rightarrow \pi^*(\text{ligand})$ transition. The complexes, 1–4 are diamagnetic, indicating the presence of metal in the +2 oxidation state. The ground state of Ru^{II} and Os^{II} in an octahedral environment is ¹A_{1g}, arising from the t^6_{2g} configuration²⁷. Thus the electronic spectra of the complexes are assigned to charge transfer transitions arising from the excitation of electrons from the metal t_{2g} level to the vacant π^* molecular orbitals of the diimine group of the ligands. Large band width ($\Delta\lambda > 30 \text{ nm}$) may insist to consider mixing of other transitions like LLCT or ILCT with this band. DFT calculation has

Fig. S1. Mass spectrum of (a) $[\text{Ru}(\text{H})(\text{CO})(\text{L}^2)(\text{PPh}_3)_2]\text{PF}_6$ (2) and (b) $[\text{OsH}(\text{CO})(\text{L}^2)(\text{PPh}_3)_2]\text{PF}_6$ (4).

Table S1. Microanalytical data Calculated (Found)% and mass spectral data in CH₃CN

Comps.	C	H	N	Isotopic mass
L ¹	72.11 (71.92)	4.95 (5.00)	22.94 (23.08)	—
L ²	65.21 (65.45)	4.38 (4.30)	30.42 (30.25)	—
[RuH(CO)(L ¹)(PPh ₃) ₂](PF ₆) (1)	58.66 (58.41)	4.10 (4.19)	4.28 (4.34)	832.1, 835.1, 836.1, 837.1, 838.1(100%), 839.1, 841.1, 842.1
[RuH(CO)(L ²)(PPh ₃) ₂](PF ₆) (2)	57.38 (57.12)	4.00 (4.08)	5.69 (5.53)	833.3, 836.3, 837.3, 838.3, 839.3(100%), 841.3, 842.3, 843.3
[OsH(CO)(L ¹)(PPh ₃) ₂](PF ₆) (3)	53.78 (53.53)	3.76 (3.82)	3.92 (3.98)	924.3, 925.3, 926.3, 928.3(100%), 929.3, 930.3
[OsH(CO)(L ²)(PPh ₃) ₂](PF ₆) (4)	52.62 (52.80)	3.66 (3.58)	5.22 (5.16)	925.4, 926.4, 927.4, 929.4(100%), 930.4, 931.4

Table 1. FT-IR (KBr disc) and UV-Visible (in CH₃CN) spectral data

Comps.	IR data in KBr disc (cm ⁻¹)				λ_{\max} in nm (ϵ , M ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)
	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{CO})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{H})$	$\nu(\text{PF}_6)$	
L ¹	1605	—	—	—	297(2986); 272(336) ^b
L ²	1606	—	—	—	296(2870); 276(1473) ^b
[RuH(CO)(PPh ₃)(L ¹)]PF ₆ (1)	1588, 1612	1954	2062	841	497(784) ^b ; 315(7506) ^b ; 288(10374); 265(2171) ^b
[RuH(CO)(PPh ₃)(L ²)]PF ₆ (2)	1590, 1620	1953	2073	841	486(757) ^b ; 313(8454) ^b ; 281(11751); 266(11178)
[OsH(CO)(PPh ₃)(L ¹)]PF ₆ (3)	1585, 1610	1942	2092	841	531(143) ^b ; 303(6078) ^b ; 287(7646); 263(1150)
[OsH(CO)(PPh ₃)(L ²)]PF ₆ (4)	1585, 1615	1942	2091	842	533(205) ^b ; 288(7586) ^b ; 281(7844); 260(6345)

Fig. 1. UV-Vis spectra of L¹ (—); [RuH(CO)(PPh₃)₂(L¹)]PF₆ (1) (—) and [OsH(CO)(PPh₃)₂(L¹)]PF₆ (3) (—) the inset picture show the lower energy bands of 1 (—) and 3 (—) in acetonitrile.

been carried out to explain the electronic structure and spectra of the complexes (*vide infra*).

Ligands exhibit emission at 365 (L¹) and 366 nm (L²) upon irradiation at 298 nm (L¹) and 295 nm (L²) in acetonitrile at room temperature (Fig. 2). The complexes are nonemissive which may be due to penetration of ligand centred excited states into the L-S coupled states of M-CO motif or dissociation of M-H bond upon excitation.

The ¹H NMR spectra of the complexes are recorded in CDCl₃ solution. The proton numbering pattern is shown in Scheme 1. The proton signals have been assigned (Table 2; representative figures are given in Supplementary materials : Figs. S2 and S3) based on spin-spin interaction and on comparison with the free ligand data. Ligands exhibit a singlet at the most downfield position which is assigned to CH=N (7-H) at ~8.7 ppm. The signals at *ca.* 8.5–7.7 ppm refer to pyridine-H (3-H–6-H) or pyrimidine-H (4-H–6-H) and the protons, 10-H–13-H, appear at 7.2–7.6 ppm. The most significant observation is the appearance of triplet M-H signal at –9.50 to –9.60 ppm (*J* 22–24 Hz) for [MH(CO)(PPh₃)₂(L)]PF₆. Triplet

Fig. 2. Fluorescence spectra of L¹ (—) and L² (---) in acetonitrile upon excitation at 298 and 295 nm respectively.

ponses are observed. One of them is quasireversible ($\Delta E_p \geq 120$ mV) and the second one appears at < -1.2 V which is irreversible^{27,28}. Ligand reduction of azoheterocycle complexes appear at negative potential^{6,7,28}. The chelated ligand belongs to diimine family isoelectronic to azoimine and can accommodate two electrons. On comparing with literature⁶ the reductive responses may be due to accommodation of electrons in the imine dominated function.

Reaction of [MH(CO)(PPh₃)₂(L)]PF₆ with AgNO₃ :

The reduction of AgNO₃ with [MH(CO)(PPh₃)₂(L)]PF₆ in presence of PVP as stabilising agent has synthesised Ag-nano-particles (AgNPs) in *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF). So-generated AgNPs, in its UV-Visible absorption spectra, show λ_{max} centred at 420 nm along with suppression of band at ~ 500 nm initially present in the

Table 2. ¹H NMR of the compounds in CDCl₃

Comps.	δ ppm (J Hz)										
	3H ^b	4H	5H ^c	6H ^b	8H ^a	11H ^b	12H ^d	13H ^d	14H ^b	M-H ^c	PPh ₃
L ¹	6.70 (7.9)	7.22 ^d	6.58 (6.2)	8.28 (4.8)	8.57	7.63 (8.0)	7.59	7.12	8.3 (4.8)	-	-
L ²	-	8.29 ^b (4.7)	6.57 (6.3)	8.29 (4.7)	8.58	7.21 (7.1)	7.63	7.13	8.29 (4.7)	-	-
1	7.16 (7.9)	7.23 ^d	6.56 (6.2)	8.15 (6.8)	9.37	7.65 (7.0)	7.91	7.49	8.80 (4.6)	-11.68 (20.6)	7.18-7.41
2	-	8.79 ^b (4.8)	6.52 (6.1)	8.38 (5.9)	9.51	7.41 (7.0)	7.92	7.17	8.80 (4.8)	-11.72 (20.1)	7.19-7.39
3	7.19 (7.8)	7.26 ^d	6.59 (6.2)	8.21 (5.2)	9.41	7.70 (7.2)	7.90	7.50	8.78 (4.4)	-12.13 (18.6)	7.21-7.42
4	-	8.77 ^b (4.3)	6.47 (6.2)	8.25 (4.8)	9.56	7.48 (6.8)	7.95	7.35	8.77 (4.3)	-13.70 (23.5)	7.19-7.40

^aSinglet; ^bDoublet; ^cTriplet; ^dMultiplet.

splitting pattern arises from coupling with two ³¹P nuclei. PPh₃ shows multiplet at 7.2-7.4 ppm.

Electrochemistry :

The electron transfer behaviour are summarized in Table 2. The complexes show both oxidative and reductive responses (Table 3, Fig. 3) in CH₃CN solutions with a platinum working electrode (+ve to Ag/AgCl) in the potential range 0.0 to 1.5 V. The voltammogram is quasireversible in nature which is evident from ($\Delta E_p > 120$ mV). The nature of voltammogram does not change with scan rate (50-250 mV s⁻¹). The oxidative couples corresponds to M^{III}/M^{II} and M^{IV}/M^{III} redox reactions. On scanning to negative direction (0 to -1.5 V) two redox res-

ponses are observed. One of them is quasireversible ($\Delta E_p \geq 120$ mV) and the second one appears at < -1.2 V which is irreversible^{27,28}. Ligand reduction of azoheterocycle complexes appear at negative potential^{6,7,28}. The chelated ligand belongs to diimine family isoelectronic to azoimine and can accommodate two electrons. On comparing with literature⁶ the reductive responses may be due to accommodation of electrons in the imine dominated function.

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Fig. S2. ^1H NMR spectrum of (L^2) in CDCl_3 .

Fig. S3. ^1H NMR spectrum of $[\text{RuH}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)_2(L^2)]\text{PF}_6$ (**2**) in CDCl_3 .

Table 3. Cyclic voltammetric data^a

Complexes	Cyclic voltammetric data ^a			Ligand reduction ^b
	M ^{III} /M ^{II}	M ^{IV} /M ^{III}		
[RuH(CO)(PPh ₃) ₂ (L ¹)]PF ₆ (1)	0.75 (160)	-	-1.24	
[RuH(CO)(PPh ₃) ₂ (L ²)]PF ₆ (2)	0.76 (155)	-	-1.26	
[OsH(CO)(PPh ₃)(L ¹)]PF ₆ (3)	0.58 (170)	1.18 (165)	-1.26	
[OsH(CO)(PPh ₃)(L ²)]PF ₆ (4)	0.57 (180)	1.16 (170)	-1.25	

^aSolvent MeCN, Pt-disk working electrode, Ag/AgCl reference electrode, Pt wire auxiliary electrode, [nBu₄N][ClO₄] supporting electrolyte. $E = 0.5 (E_{pa} + E_{pc})$, V; $\Delta E_p = |E_{pa} - E_{pc}|$, mV; E_{pc} (cathodic-peak-potential), E_{pa} (anodic-peak-potential).

^b E_{pc} (cathodic-peak-potential).

Fig. 3. Cyclic voltammogram of [RuH(CO)(PPh₃)₂(L¹)]PF₆ (1) in acetonitrile using Pt-milli working electrode, Ag-AgCl/Cl⁻ reference, Pt-auxiliary and [n-NBu₄](ClO₄) supporting electrolyte at scan rate 50 mV s⁻¹.

mid and platelets absorb in the blue, green and red part of the spectrum, respectively. In all the cases the SPR peak wavelength increases with size, as expected. The UV-Visible spectra for the AgNPs are shown in Fig. 4. The distribution of shapes in the sample is broad, and a significant amount of NPs are not spherical. The presence of AgNPs with pentagonal and triangular cross-sections could be responsible for the absorption at longer wavelengths. Thus, it is clear that the characteristic absorption of these AgNPs arises from the contribution of

Fig. 4. UV-Vis spectra of [RuH(CO)(PPh₃)₂(L²)]PF₆ (2) (—); upon addition of AgNO₃ after 2 h (—) and after 41 h (—) using PVP as a stabilizer. The complexes and AgNO₃ are in 1 mmol ratio (5 ml of 5 mmol complex and 5 ml of 1 mmol AgNO₃) and 5 mg PVP is added.

Fig. 5. Reduction of AgNO₃ by (a) [RuH(CO)(PPh₃)₂(L¹)]PF₆ and (b) [OsH(CO)(PPh₃)₂(L¹)]PF₆ in DMF in presence of PVP as stabiliser and the HR TEM images and size distribution histogram of Ag nanoparticles.

different shapes and sizes, which agrees with the TEM observations (Fig. 5). The AgNPs synthesised by the reduction of [OsH(CO)(PPh₃)₂(L)]PF₆ are larger in size than

that of $[\text{RuH}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{L})]\text{PF}_6$ complexes. This accounts on efficient reducing activity of ruthenium complexes. Average particle size obtained by the reduction of AgNO_3 using osmium complexes $[\text{OsH}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{L})]\text{PF}_6$ (3, 4) is about 109 nm and of block size while particle size varies from 50–75 nm and maximum number of particles belongs to about 56 nm when $[\text{RuH}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{L})]\text{PF}_6$ (1, 2) are used as reducing agents.

DFT calculation : electronic structure, spectra and redox properties :

The DFT calculations are used to establish the electronic structure, interpretation of spectra and their redox properties. The optimized structure of these molecules is developed (Table 4, Fig. 6) using Gaussian 03 analyses package. The orbital energies along with contributions from the ligands and metal and some of the MOs are

Table 4. Selected bond length and bond angle of $[\text{RuH}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{L}^1)]^+$ (1), $[\text{RuH}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{L}^2)]^+$ (2), $[\text{OsH}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{L}^1)]^+$ (3) and $[\text{OsH}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{L}^2)]^+$ (4) from TD-DFT calculation bond length in (Å) and the bond angle in ($^\circ$)

Bond parameter	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
Bond lengths (Å) :				
M-H	1.62579	1.59683	1.63947	1.63559
M-C(1)	1.83447	1.85002	1.88099	1.86548
M-N(1)	2.09454	2.16549	2.20011	2.21023
M-N(2)	2.19494	2.20859	2.22152	2.19771
M-P(1)	2.47581	2.46033	2.49182	2.45366
M-P(2)	2.46400	2.47561	2.47313	2.48197
C(1)-O	1.16275	1.16332	1.17193	1.16492
Bond angle in ($^\circ$) :				
C(1)-M-N(1)	177.42370	178.23952	177.10930	175.96034
C(1)-M-N(2)	102.55862	102.51622	102.61436	102.66952
C(1)-M-H	87.49665	88.01054	89.07703	90.19378
C(1)-M-P(1)	91.35714	89.56653	90.50874	90.98000
C(1)-M-P(2)	87.72085	89.66691	89.00379	90.82519
N(1)-M-N(2)	77.54635	75.86225	74.83715	73.59454
N(1)-M-H	92.59465	93.64852	93.54019	93.55878
N(1)-M-P(1)	91.21407	89.95094	91.01149	87.85869
N(1)-M-P(2)	89.71238	91.09896	89.92456	91.16980
N(2)-M-H	169.14250	168.97548	167.96181	167.12890
N(2)-M-P(1)	91.22450	96.86224	93.52871	95.06714
N(2)-M-P(2)	97.30715	92.96034	96.31988	97.05518
P(1)-M-H	84.37207	86.36041	83.38494	85.03327
P(1)-M-P(2)	171.41622	170.07855	170.00517	167.03827
P(2)-M-H	87.06134	83.72720	86.62548	82.12626

Fig. 6a. DFT computed optimized structure of $[\text{OsH}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{L}^1)]\text{PF}_6$ (3) H and PF_6 atoms are omitted rather than Os-H for clarity.

Fig. 6b. DFT computed optimized structure of $[\text{OsH}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{L}^2)]\text{PF}_6$ (4) H and PF_6 atoms are omitted rather than Os-H for clarity.

given in Fig. 7 with contributions from the ligands and metal, energy. The energy correlation of MOs of ruthenium (1, 2) and osmium (3, 4) complexes shows that the highest energy occupied MOs (HOMO) are better stabilized in ruthenium complexes than osmium complexes and the difference in energy is 0.15–0.20 eV (Fig. 8). The HOMO-LUMO energy gap is 0.11–0.13 eV lower in

Fig. 7a. Some selected MO's of $[\text{RuH}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{L}^1)]^+$ (1).

Fig. 7b. Some selected MO's of $[\text{OsH}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{L}^1)]^+$ (3).

Fig. 8a. Energy correlation, composition and transition energies among MO's of $[\text{RuH}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{L}^1)]^+$ (1) and $[\text{OsH}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{L}^1)]^+$ (3).

Fig. 8b. Energy correlation, composition and transition energies among MO's of $[\text{RuH}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{L}^2)]^+$ (2) and $[\text{OsH}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{L}^2)]^+$ (4).

osmium complexes compare to corresponding ruthenium complexes. The HOMO carries >60% of M (Ru, Os) contribution. The LUMO and LUMO+1 have >90% ligand (π^*) character. Other higher energy occupied MOs (HOMO-1, HOMO-2 etc.) contain PPh_3 as major contributor (>80%) with minor contribution from metal.

To understand the nature of electronic transitions, TD-DFT calculations in acetonitrile have been performed on the optimized structures of **1-4** (Table 4, Fig. 6). The low energy band correspond to HOMO/HOMO-1 \rightarrow LUMO,

$\text{PPh}_3(\pi)/\text{M}(d\pi)\rightarrow\text{L}(\pi^*)$ transitions. The composition of occupied MOs inspects that these are not pure MLCT transition rather admixture of MLCT and $\text{PPh}_3(\pi)\rightarrow\text{L}(\pi^*)$. For osmium complexes this band is observed at lower energy region compare to corresponding ruthenium complexes (Fig. 8). The transitions at around 310 nm is a mixed inter-ligand transitions, $\text{L}(\pi)/\text{PPh}_3(\pi)\rightarrow\text{L}(\pi^*)$ while the strong band at ~ 290 nm is a intra-ligand $\pi\rightarrow\pi^*$ transitions of electrons localized on the azomethine group of the Schiff base, $\text{L}(\pi)\rightarrow\text{L}(\pi^*)$ (Table 5).

Table 5a. Calculated transitions obtained from TD-DFT computation of optimized geometry of $[\text{RuH}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{L}^1)]^+$ (1)

Excited state	Wave length (λ , nm)	Osc. strength (f)	Energy (eV)	Transition	Character
1	525.6	0.013	2.3590	(75%) HOMO \rightarrow LUMO	$\text{Ru}(d\pi)\rightarrow\text{L}(\pi^*)$, MLCT
2	464.9	0.017	2.8182	(52%) HOMO-1 \rightarrow LUMO (32%) HOMO-4 \rightarrow LUMO	$\text{PPh}_3(\pi)\rightarrow\text{L}(\pi^*)$, ILCT $\text{Ru}(d\pi)\rightarrow\text{L}(\pi^*)$, MLCT
12	361.2	0.010	3.4322	(67%) HOMO-10 \rightarrow LUMO	$\text{PPh}_3(\pi)\rightarrow\text{L}(\pi^*)$, ILCT
13	350.9	0.070	3.5330	(41%) HOMO-12 \rightarrow LUMO (35%) HOMO-13 \rightarrow LUMO	$\text{L}(\pi)/\text{PPh}_3(\pi)\rightarrow\text{L}(\pi^*)$, ILCT $\text{PPh}_3(\pi)\rightarrow\text{L}(\pi^*)$, ILCT
17	323.5	0.091	3.6093	(77%) HOMO-16 \rightarrow LUMO	$\text{L}(\pi)\rightarrow\text{L}(\pi^*)$, ILCT

Table 5b. Calculated transitions obtained from TD-DFT computation of optimized geometry of $[\text{RuH}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{L}^2)]^+$ (2)

Excited state	Wave length (λ , nm)	Osc. strength (f)	Energy (eV)	Transition	Character
1	546.6	0.020	2.2682	(74%) HOMO \rightarrow LUMO	$\text{Ru}(d\pi)\rightarrow\text{L}(\pi^*)$, MLCT
2	486.2	0.012	2.5501	(63%) HOMO-1 \rightarrow LUMO	$\text{Ru}(d\pi)/\text{PPh}_3(\pi)\rightarrow\text{L}(\pi^*)$, (MLCT, ILCT)
5	402.3	0.010	3.0820	(38%) HOMO-3 \rightarrow LUMO (25%) HOMO-4 \rightarrow LUMO	$\text{Ru}(d\pi)\rightarrow\text{L}(\pi^*)$, MLCT $\text{PPh}_3(\pi)\rightarrow\text{L}(\pi^*)$, ILCT
14	328.9	0.067	3.7698	(51%) HOMO-15 \rightarrow LUMO (27%) HOMO-16 \rightarrow LUMO	$\text{L}(\pi)\rightarrow\text{L}(\pi^*)$, ILCT
19	307.3	0.093	4.0348	(47%) HOMO-20 \rightarrow LUMO (33%) HOMO-19 \rightarrow LUMO	$\text{PPh}_3(\pi)\rightarrow\text{L}(\pi^*)$, ILCT $\text{L}(\pi)\rightarrow\text{L}(\pi^*)$, ILCT
20	301.7	0.119	4.1097	(39%) HOMO-19 \rightarrow LUMO (21%) HOMO-20 \rightarrow LUMO	$\text{L}(\pi)\rightarrow\text{L}(\pi^*)$, ILCT $\text{PPh}_3(\pi)\rightarrow\text{L}(\pi^*)$, ILCT

Table 5c. Calculated transitions obtained from TD-DFT computation of optimized geometry of $[\text{OsH}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{L}^1)]^+$ (3)

Excited state	Wave length (λ , nm)	Osc. strength (f)	Energy (eV)	Transition	Character
1	530.6	0.024	2.3367	(79%) HOMO \rightarrow LUMO	$\text{Os}(d\pi)\rightarrow\text{L}(\pi^*)$, MLCT
2	466.7	0.006	2.6568	(44%) HOMO-2 \rightarrow LUMO (39%) HOMO-1 \rightarrow LUMO	$\text{Os}(d\pi)/\text{PPh}_3(\pi)\rightarrow\text{L}(\pi^*)$, (MLCT, ILCT)
3	451.9	0.016	2.7433	(46%) HOMO-3 \rightarrow LUMO (26%) HOMO-1 \rightarrow LUMO	$\text{Os}(d\pi)/\text{PPh}_3(\pi)\rightarrow\text{L}(\pi^*)$, (MLCT, ILCT)
15	343.4	0.093	3.6101	(43%) HOMO-12 \rightarrow LUMO (22%) HOMO-15 \rightarrow LUMO	$\text{L}(\pi)/\text{PPh}_3(\pi)\rightarrow\text{L}(\pi^*)$, ILCT
19	318.9	0.107	3.8874	(57%) HOMO-16 \rightarrow LUMO	$\text{L}(\pi)\rightarrow\text{L}(\pi^*)$, ILCT

Table 5d. Calculated transitions obtained from TD-DFT computation of optimized geometry of $[\text{OsH}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{L}^2)]^+$ (4)

Excited state	Wave length (λ , nm)	Osc. strength (f)	Energy (eV)	Transition	Character
1	567.1	0.027	2.1862	(81%) HOMO \rightarrow LUMO	Os(d π) \rightarrow L(π^*), MLCT
2	509.2	0.031	2.4349	(72%) HOMO-1 \rightarrow LUMO	Os(d π) \rightarrow L(π^*), MLCT
3	483.7	0.013	2.5633	(49%) HOMO-3 \rightarrow LUMO (31%) HOMO-4 \rightarrow LUMO	Os(d π)/PPh ₃ (π) \rightarrow L(π^*), (MLCT, ILCT)
15	341.5	0.121	3.6307	(43%) HOMO-16 \rightarrow LUMO (22%) HOMO-15 \rightarrow LUMO	L(π) \rightarrow L(π^*), ILCT
20	301.6	0.091	4.1110	(45%) HOMO-19 \rightarrow LUMO (31%) HOMO-20 \rightarrow LUMO	L(π) \rightarrow L(π^*), ILCT L(π)/PPh ₃ (π) \rightarrow L(π^*), ILCT

The oxidation is electron extraction from occupied MO(s) and reduction is referred to electron accommodation to unoccupied MO(s). First oxidation may be assigned to $\text{M}^{\text{II}}\rightarrow\text{M}^{\text{III}}$ in both Ru and Os complexes because the HOMO is constituted by >60% of metal contribution. The lower potential for osmium complexes is well supported by higher energy of HOMO relative to the corresponding ruthenium complexes (by 0.11–0.13 eV). In addition the second oxidation for **3** and **4** is assigned to $\text{M}^{\text{III}}\rightarrow\text{M}^{\text{IV}}$ which is not observed for **1** and **2**. It may be due to higher stability of singly occupied molecular orbital (SOMO) for the latter complexes. The LUMO is basically made of ligand orbitals (>90%) and the reduction is explained as electron accommodation into the LUMO.

Experimental

Materials :

N-[(2-Pyridyl)methylidene]-2-aminopyridine (L^1) and (L^2) were synthesized by mixing 1 : 1 equivalent of pyridine-2-carboxaldehyde and the corresponding amine in dry methanol and refluxed the mixture for 6 h. $\text{RuH}(\text{Cl})(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)_3$ and $\text{OsH}(\text{Cl})(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)_3$ were prepared by reported method^{15,33}. 2-Aminopyridine, 2-aminopyrimidine, pyridine-2-carboxaldehyde and polyvinyl pyrrolidone (PVP) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich and all other organic chemicals and inorganic salts were available from Sisco Research Lab, Mumbai, India. The purification of acetonitrile and preparation of *n*-tetra butylammonium perchlorate $[\text{nBu}_4\text{N}][\text{ClO}_4]$ for electrochemical work were done as before⁶. Dinitrogen was purified by bubbling through an alkaline pyrogallol

solution. All other chemicals and solvents were of reagent grade and were used without further purification.

Physical measurements :

Microanalytical data (C, H, N) were collected on Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHNS/O elemental analyzer. Spectroscopic data were obtained using the following instruments : UV-Vis spectra, Perkin-Elmer; model Lambda 25, FL spectra by using LS55 spectrofluorimeter. IR spectra (KBr disk, 4000–400 cm^{-1}), Perkin-Elmer; model RX-1, ¹H NMR spectra, Bruker (AC) 300 MHz FTNMR spectrometer. Molar conductances were measured using a Systronics conductivity meter 304 model using *ca.* 10^{-3} M solutions in nitromethane. Electrochemical measurements were performed using computer-controlled PAR model 250 VersaStat electrochemical instruments with Pt-disk electrodes. All measurements were carried out under nitrogen environment at 298 K with reference to Ag/AgCl, Cl^- electrode in acetonitrile using $[\text{nBu}_4\text{N}][\text{ClO}_4]$ as supporting electrolyte. The reported potentials are uncorrected for junction potential. High Resolution Transmission Electron Microscopic (HR TEM) studies of the particles were carried out at a resolution of 1.9 Angstrom unit of JEOL, JEM-2100 Electron Microscope from Japan. HR TEM specimens were prepared by placing micro drops of micro emulsion solutions on a carbon film supported by a copper grid.

Synthesis of complexes :

N-[(2-Pyridyl)methylidene]-2-aminopyridine (L^1) and *N*-[(2-pyridyl)methylidene]-2-aminopyrimidine (L^2) :

In 30 ml dry methanol 2-aminopyridine (1.213 mg, 12.9 mmol) was dissolved, to it pyridine-2-carboxaldehyde (1.38 g, 12.9 mmol) was added and the mixture

was refluxed for 6 h in the presence of molecular sieves, it was filtered and collect in a beaker, upon slow evaporation of solvent crystalline precipitate was appeared, it was collected and washed with few ml of cold methanol and dried over CaCl₂ desiccator. Yield was 64%. *N*-[(2-Pyridyl)methylidene]-2-aminopyrimidine (L²) was also prepared following identical procedure. Yield 61%. Microanalytical data : Found (Calcd.) % for L¹; Found : C, 72.22; H, 4.87; N, 23.02. Calcd. for C₁₁H₉N₃ : C, 72.13; H, 4.92; N, 22.95; L² : Found : C, 65.31; H, 4.43; N, 3.00. Calcd. for C₁₀H₈N₄ : C, 65.22; H, 4.35; N, 3.04.

[RuH(CO)(PPh₃)₂(L¹)]PF₆ (1) and [RuH(CO)(PPh₃)₂(L¹)]PF₆ (2) :

To a suspension of RuH(Cl)(CO)(PPh₃)₃ (200 mg, 0.21 mmol) in dry MeCN (20 ml) AgNO₃ (36.1 mg, 0.21 mmol) was added in stirring condition and the stirring was continued for 1 and a half hours. The formed AgCl was separated through G-4. With the filtrate *N*-[(2-pyridyl)methylidene]-2-aminopyridine (L¹) (39.8 mg, 0.22 mmol) was added in the same solvent (10 ml). The solution was stirred and refluxed for 12 h under dinitrogen. The colourless solution was turned into red. It was cooled and filtered. The filtrate was then evaporated slowly in air. It was dissolved in 10 ml of methanol and aqueous solution (5 ml) of NH₄PF₆ (200 mg) was added into this solution, light red precipitate appeared; filtered, washed with cold water and n-hexane, dried over CaCl₂ desiccators *in vacuo*. The yield was 128 mg (62%). [RuH(CO)(PPh₃)₂(L²)]PF₆ (2) was prepared (yield 61%) following the above procedure. Microanalytical data : Found and (Calcd.) % for [RuH(CO)(PPh₃)₂(L¹)]PF₆ (1); Found : C, 58.60; H, 4.03; N, 4.35. Calcd. for C₄₈H₄₀N₃OP₃F₆Ru : C, 58.65; H, 4.07; N, 4.28; [RuH(CO)(PPh₃)₂(L²)]PF₆ (2); Found : C, 57.44; H, 4.03; N, 5.80. Calcd. for C₄₇H₃₉N₄OP₃F₆Ru : C, 57.37; H, 3.97; N, 5.70.

[OsH(CO)(PPh₃)₂(L¹)] PF₆ (3) and [OsH(CO)(PPh₃)₂(L²)] PF₆ (4) :

To a suspension of OsH(Cl)(CO)(PPh₃)₃ (210 mg, 0.20 mmol) in dry MeCN (20 ml) AgNO₃ (34.5 mg, 0.21 mmol) was added in stirring condition and the stirring was continued for 2 and a half hours. The AgCl formed was separated through G-4. To the filtrate *N*-[(2-pyridyl)methylidene]-2-aminopyridine (L¹) (37.1 mg, 0.20

mmol) in the same solvent (10 ml) was added. The solution was stirred and refluxed for 48 h under dinitrogen. The colourless solution was turned to red violet which then cooled and filtered. The filtrate was evaporated slowly in air. The residue was dissolved in methanol (10 ml) and aqueous solution (5 ml) of NH₄PF₆ (200 mg) was added into this solution which afforded red violet precipitate appeared that was filtered, washed with cold water followed by n-hexane and dried desiccators *in vacuo*. The yield was 119 mg (55%). [OsH(CO)(PPh₃)₂(L¹)]PF₆ (3) was prepared (yield 56%) following the procedure described above. Microanalytical data : Found and Calcd. % for [OsH(CO)(PPh₃)₂(L¹)]PF₆ (3). Found : C, 53.83; H, 3.80; N, 3.80. Calcd. for C₄₈H₄₀N₃OP₃F₆Os : C, 53.77; H, 3.73; N, 3.92; [OsH(CO)(PPh₃)₂(L²)]PF₆ (4); Found : C, 52.55; H, 3.60; N, 5.15. Calcd. for C₄₇H₃₉N₄OP₃F₆Os : C, 52.60; H, 3.64; N, 5.22.

Preparation AgNPs by reduction of AgNO₃ using [RuH(CO)(PPh₃)₂(L¹)]PF₆ in DMF :

To a 20 ml AgNO₃ (1.0 mM) in alcoholic solution was added to [RuH(CO)(PPh₃)₂(L¹)]PF₆ (10 ml, 5.0 mM) in DMF, with stirring in the presence of PVP used as stabilizing agent. The reaction was carried in an ice bath and with protection from light. The formation of AgNPs was confirmed by absorption spectroscopy.

Computation :

Full geometry optimizations were carried out using the density functional theory method at the B3LYP level for 1-4³⁴. The 6-31G(d) basis set was used for C, H and N atoms and 6-31+G(d) for P atoms while SDD basis set with effective core potential was employed for ruthenium and osmium atoms³⁵. The vibrational frequency calculations were performed to ensure that the optimized geometries represent the local minima and there are only positive eigen values. All calculations were performed with Gaussian03 program package³⁶ with the aid of the GaussView visualization program³⁷. Natural bond orbital analyses were performed using the NBO 3.1 module of Gaussian03³⁸. Vertical electronic excitations based on B3LYP optimized geometries was computed using the time-dependent density functional theory (TD-DFT) formalism³⁹ in acetonitrile using conductor-like polarizable continuum model (CPCM)⁴⁰. GaussSum⁴¹ was used to calculate the fractional contributions of various groups to each molecular orbital.

Conclusion :

N-[(2-Pyridyl)methyliden]-2-aminopyridine (L^1) and *N*-[(2-pyridyl)methyliden]-2-aminopyrimidine (L^2) are used to synthesise $[MH(CO)(PPh_3)_2(L)]PF_6$ complexes ($M = Ru^{II}$ and Os^{II}) and are characterized by microanalytical and spectroscopic results. The electrochemical studies show Ru^{III}/Ru^{II} , Os^{III}/Os^{II} and Os^{IV}/Os^{III} couples. The DFT computation is carried out to identify the optimized structures and to explain the spectral and redox properties. The complexes reduce $AgNO_3$ and have synthesised AgNPs. Ruthenium compounds are better reducing agent to synthesise AgNPs than osmium complexes.

Supplementary materials :

To save space in the published article some of the figures and tables are added as Supplementary materials. Supplementary figure are mass spectra (Fig. S1), 1H NMR spectra (Figs. S2 and S3); Supplementary tables : Mass spectral data (Table S1).

Acknowledgement

Financial support from DST, PURSE and UGC-CAS are thankfully acknowledged.

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